

Gender Role and Politeness Strategies Used by *Banjarese and American*

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ABSTRACT: *This study aimed 1) to find the politeness strategy that is used by Banjarese and American to their relatives by using Yassi system of politeness which adaption from Brown and Levinson and Scollon and Scollon by adding Kinship (K) 2) to discover the influence of gender in using politeness strategy among Banjarese and American. The source of data was utterances by Banjarese and American. It used politeness theory of Brown & Levinson; Bald on-record, Positive, Negative, and Off-record. The study used descriptive qualitative method and the data were the transcription of utterances by Banjarese and American. The result of the study found that that Banjarese used positive politeness, negative politeness, and off-record to their relatives. Banjarese male paid more respect to their relatives in using politeness strategy. Banjarese female concentrated on expressing their personal feeling and better at giving compliment. In addition, American tend to use positive politeness, negative politeness, and bald on record. While American male often use politeness marker to address their interlocutor to make the interlocutor feel accepted. Furthermore, American female tend to exaggerate their utterance which make the interlocutor feel accepted and appreciated. This study is able to encourage the society to apply the politeness in better way which creates the harmony in the social interaction.*

Keyword: *Politeness strategy, Banjarese, Brown & Levinson, Kinship (K)*

I. INTRODUCTION

People express their idea or feeling through language. As a human, people use language as a tool to communicate with each other. In communication, an utterance has a certain purpose, intention, and meaning. Pragmatic is one of the branches of linguistic study that is concerned with the study of meaning by the speaker and interpreted by the listener (Andini et al., 2021; Saleh et al., 2021). The factors of place, time, and the relationship between speaker and listener affect the meaning of certain utterances. Pragmatics is related to the study of utterances communicated by the speaker or writer and interpreted by the listener or reader (Yule, 1996). Therefore, it can be concluded that pragmatics is a study that studies meaning because it focuses on the intent and purpose of the speaker. According to Glaser, (2009) pragmatics is the study of how the meaning of discourse is created in particular sender and receiver (Odebunmi, 2013). Based on the explanation above, it is concluded that pragmatics has a role in understanding the context contained in utterances. In addition, Brown and Levinson stated pragmatics is the study of the use of language in communications or the study of the meaning of utterances concerning the contexts, which involves how the speaker produces an utterance to deliver their intention and how the listener interprets it (Brown & Levinson, 2011).

Moreover, in pragmatics that one of the key things accomplished through language in interaction is the delivery of social actions (White et al., 1963). Politeness is one of the pragmatic competencies that should be considered in communicate. This strategy determines the success of communication between the participants. Politeness possesses several social functions, which create harmonious interactions, show respect, etc. Politeness refers to social or ethical behavior that participants must use in communicating so that positive

communication occurs between participants (Bachriani et al., 2018). This strategy is also believed to be a compelling concept to avoid conflicts between individuals that have the potential to become conflicts on a larger scale, such as between groups or between ethnic groups (Yassi, 2018). According to Brown and (Brown & Levinson, 2011) the politeness strategy minimizes face-threatening acts (FTA). When people have a conversation, there is a possibility in threatening the hearer's face (Yassi, 2018). FTA is an act that inherently damages the face of the addressee or the speaker by acting in opposition to the wants and desires of the other (Sapitri et al., 2019). Establishing good communication between the speaker and the interlocutor requires rules that regulate them. Social aspects such as social order, social rank, age, environment, and especially gender must be involved when communicating or studying the language. Politeness and gender role have influenced the social interaction (Sukmawaty et al., 2022). It has been concern for many researchers especially in language studies and also considered as one of the important aspect that affect politeness strategy used. Gender is a concept to identify the differences between men and women in socio-cultural impressions (Ambarita et al., 2020; Sahib & Rahman, 2021). In addition, gender has significant effects on language use between men and women, such as lexical, grammatical, and pragmatic (Kuntjara, 2014). It influences the perspective in using language when participants interact. Several studies show that men and women have different ways of communicating that shows men and woman have their way of speaking or expressing their ideas or minds to interlocutors. The experts have investigated the relationship between politeness and gender particularly in relation to gender stereotypes. They believe men and women have different language behavior. In general, men tend to use impolite form, they often use direct and assertive speech variety while women is categorized polite and deferent (Mills, 2004). The problem of politeness and gender as speech construction is still a concern of linguists for decades.

Brown and Levinson categorized politeness strategy into 5 types strategy: Bald on Record (The speaker utter the utterance directly without any ambiguity), Positive Politeness (The speaker want to make the hearer comfortable and show that the speaker have same goals or desire), Negative Politeness (This strategy prevent or minimize the threats to the negative face of the interlocutor and concern to respect behavior), Off-Record (The speaker deliver their utterance indirectly and let the addressee to decide how to interpret it), and the last is Don't do the FTA (The speaker does nothing and keep silent). Indonesia is a country which categorized as multilingual country has its characteristics in local language (Sahib et al., 2021). Based on the explanation above, this paper will discuss the politeness strategy that is used among *Banjarese* (South Borneo) and American to their relatives and family also the influence of gender on politeness strategy used by *Banjarese* (South Borneo) and American using the system of politeness proposed by Yassi (2018). The systems of politeness strategies on social interaction result from the adaption and development of politeness theory by Brown & Levinson and Scollon & Scollon by adding Kinship (K).

I. PREVIOUS STUDIES

The studies of politeness strategies have been studied by many researches, the findings from these studies become references to conduct this research. Similar research by Mahmud (2013) entitled "The Roles of Social Status, Age, Gender, Familiarity, and Situation in Being Polite for *Bugis* Society". The study focused on the politeness strategy of *Bugis* people influenced by several aspects such as social status, gender, age, familiarity, and situation. This research has similarities in analyzing politeness strategy used Brown and Levinson's theory and focused on the role of gender in the politeness strategy used. The result of this study shows the important roles of social status, age, gender, familiarity, and situation in determining the level of politeness of *Bugis* people. In rural area, social status becomes the most important factor whereas in urban area, gender differences can be higher priority in applying their politeness.

Furthermore, Arapah and Mu'in (2017) conducted a research entitled "Politeness in Using *Banjarese* and American English Personal Subject Pronouns by English Department Students of *LambungMangkurat* University". It focused on the politeness strategy used among *Banjarese*, the English Department of *LambungMangkurat* University students, and Americans, especially in using personal subject pronouns. Several aspects of this research are situation, intimacy, social status, sex distinction, and marital status. The result of the

study shows that *Banjarese* and American English Pronouns are based on singular and plural distinction although *Banjarese* does not have a gender distinction as in the American English. The personal pronouns are the first, second, and third persons. English personal pronouns depend mostly on the grammatical role while *Banjarese* personal pronouns can indicate the social status, and they can be categorized as polite or impolite speakers.

Daud et al., (2018) also conducted a research entitled "Politeness Strategies of Negation Used by English and *Buginese*". This study investigated the politeness strategies *Buginese* and American people used in using negation expression and the influence of social and cultural relationships toward the politeness strategy by *Buginese* and American people when using negation expression. The results of the study explain that there are three politeness strategy are used by American and *Buginese* people in using negation which are the bald on record, positive politeness, and negative politeness. The American people tend to use those strategies in polite way to negate something by being more friendly and using the casual language with other people. Meanwhile, *Buginese* people tend to use formal language as the politeness strategies in making negation. The American often use direct strategies but the *Buginese* people chose to apply indirect negation.

The next research, from Bazzi et al., (2018) entitled politeness strategies and gender differences in the speech act of rejection among the Malays in Malaysia. This study aims to identify the positive and the negative politeness strategies that is used by both genders in making rejection and also compare the differences of both genders in making rejection. This study employs the framework of Brown and Levinson's model of politeness (1987). The researcher gathers all the data through the questionnaire involving nine different situations and formulated based on oral Discourse Complexion Task. The respondents were 50 male and 50 female students of International Islamic University Malaysia. In conclusion, male used more positive and negative politeness strategies than females when making rejection. They choose to more explanative and apologetic when making rejection.

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Based on the previous section, the objective of this study is formulated as follows: 1) to find the politeness strategy that is used by *Banjarese* and American to their relatives by using Yassi system of politeness which adaption from Brown and Levinson and Scollon and Scollon by adding Kinship (K) 2) to discover the influence of gender in using politeness strategy among *Banjarese* and American. The data will be categorized in five types of politeness strategies by Brown and Levinson.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Pragmatics is a branch of linguistics that relates to language behavior or language use based on the situation, based on the situation of the speaker or the speech partner. Pragmatics also relates to how the hearer can understand the meaning conveyed by the speaker. It is also defines as the study of contextual meaning (Glaser, 2009). This study contains the interpretation of the meaning in particular context and how the context affects the meaning. In addition, pragmatic is the study of the language use which determined by the context of society (Mey, 2006). Then, pragmatic defines as the study of the relationship between language and context (Levinson, 1983). In conclusion, this study relate to the meaning of the language and how the meaning is influenced by the context. The speech situation enables the speaker to achieve the effect of the utterance that they deliver to the hearer because vocabulary brings the speaker's intended meaning (Hanafiah et al., 2022)

1. Politeness

From the definition of 'politeness' by Lakoff, he observes that politeness is a system of interpersonal relations designed to facilitate interaction by minimizing the potential for conflict and confrontation inherent in all human interchange (Abordonado& Maria Viotti, 1998). Brown and Levinson introduced the politeness theory in 1987. It focuses on others' face. They define face as "the public self-image that every member wants to claim for himself" (Brown & Levinson, 2011). Brown and Levinson define FTA as something represented by a speaker as a threat to another individual's expectation regarding self-image (Mahmud, 2013). FTA can threaten both positive face and negative faces. In addition, the example of positive FTA such as an expression of

disapproval, criticism, felt disgusted, complaining, accusing, insulting, disagreeing, emotionally abusive, mentioning taboo topics, interrupting, and uncooperative. Then, negative FTA includes command, request, suggest, remind, threaten, warn, offer, promise, express jealousy, admiration, hate, anger, passion, etc. They claim that any rational agent will avoid this Face Threatening Acts (FTA) or apply specific strategies to minimize the threat. Politeness strategy is a strategy used to avoid or reduce the effect of self-image destruction that arises from face-threatening acts by speakers. Brown and Levinson suggested five types of politeness strategies (Brown & Levinson, 2011). These five strategies are referred to as "super strategies".

a. Bald on Record

The speaker employs this strategy with direct, clear, unambiguous way. They do not attempt to soften the face threatening-acts. The speaker does nothing to minimize the threat to the speaker's self-image. Instead, the speaker performs the speech act directly and clearly.

b. Positive Politeness

The speaker gives a positive self-image to the interlocutor. Brown and Levinson argue that positive politeness occurs in a group or environment where participants have the same goals, desires, or background knowledge. This strategy arises because the speaker wants to show a good impression of the interlocutor and indicates that the speaker wants to strengthen his social relationship with the addressee through the same desires and views between the speaker and the interlocutor.

c. Negative Politeness

Brown and Levinson stated that negative politeness strategies are actions to prevent or minimize threats to the negative face of the interlocutor. It concerns respect behavior. In conducting this strategy, the speaker would like to emphasize the hearer's relative power. All of the strategies' outputs are useful for keeping the social distance.

d. Off Record

Off record is described as an indirect strategy. Context and situation are essential elements in understanding this politeness strategy. If a speaker wants to do an FTA but wants to avoid the responsibility, they can do off-record and leave it up to the addressee to decide how to interpret it.

e. Don't do the FTA

This strategy is S avoids offending H at all with this particular FTA. In conclusion, S fails to achieve his desired communication. The speaker does nothing and keeps silent.

2. Gender

One of the crucial dimensions of language is gender. Gender is a social variable in society that affects language style. In general, gender is a difference between men and women, which can be seen in physical characteristics and behavior. Gender has been considered an essential feature in the interactions between people. Gender is a cultural concept that refers to the characteristic distinguishing between women's and men's behavior, mentality, and socio-cultural. Gender refers to psychosocial aspects of maleness and femaleness (Elliott, 2019). It can be concluded that gender is a psychosocial aspect of masculinity and femininity, whereas sex is biologically male and female.

In a study related to American society, that women are inferior and subordinate to men (Holmes & Meyerhoff, 1999). Hence, they are not to offend and express themselves politely in their verbal communication. Gender and language have long been a topic of interest among scholars. Women and men have different ways in doing communicating. Lakoff(1973) stated that women's language has another characteristic. Women tend to use 'empty adjectives' such as lovely, divined, and adorable (Svendsen, 2019). Women also use tag questions and hedges, which indicate uncertainty. Women are very concerned about using grammar and polite forms in their speech and writings. Men and women are raised differently, creating differences in the way they speak (Tannen, 1995). Women mostly speak to seek connection and intimacy, whereas men speak to show their status and independence (Gray, 1992). In conclusion, there are many differences between men and women in using language that relate to the politeness.

IV. METHOD

This research use descriptive qualitative method, this paper will discuss the politeness strategy that is used among *Banjarese* (South Borneo) and American to their relatives and family also the influence of gender on politeness strategy used by *Banjarese* (South Borneo) using the system of politeness proposed by Yassi (2018). The systems of politeness strategies on social interaction result from the adaption and development of politeness theory by Brown & Levinson by adding Kinship (K).

1. Participants

To fulfill this research, the researcher took the data from the daily conversation of the *Banjarese* people and the transcription of the conversation in American Reality Show

2. Data analysis

In this research, the writer used the politeness strategies by Brown and Levinson. First of all, the writer transcribed the utterances from the conversation of *Banjarese* and American. Then, the writer analyzed and determined the type of politeness strategies used by *Banjarese* and American.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The politeness strategies used by *Banjarese*

Datum 1 : the interaction between a male and male relatives

A : *Nah, urangnya datangan dah*
(Here, you are)

B : *Kayapa habar? Baik haja lah*
(How are you? you good?)

A : *Alhamdulillah, bengkel aman aja lo?*
(Alhamdulillah, how about your motorcycle repair shop?)

B : *Alhamdulillah, rami haja.*
(Alhamdulillah, it is good)

The data above is the interaction between a two relatives who have the same age, the conversation between them is casual and very friendly. It can be seen that the speaker employ positive politeness strategy which is notice. He asked about every aspect that relate to the hearer.

Datum 2 : the interaction between a male and female relatives

A : *Kada usah amang memandiri ini ikam tau sorang kalo kayapa harusnya ikam wan laki.* (I think you already know what I mean, the way you act to him)

B : *Ulun handak ai mang ai, tapi ulun berat hati meninggalakan ading sorangan.*
(I want to do it, but it is so hard to leave my brother)

A : *Inshaallah, inya kadapapa. Yakin ikam inya baik ja*
(Inshaallah, he will be alright. You need to be sure)

The data above is the conversation between an uncle and his niece. It can be seen that the uncle used honorific *ikam* (you) and *inya* (he/she) which considered impolite/neutral. During the conversation, the uncle used pronoun *ikam* and *inya* consistently. Meanwhile, his niece used *ulun* (I) as polite form of pronoun to show deference to her uncle. The utterance "I think you already know what I mean, the way you act to him (*kadausahamangmemandiriiniikam tau sorangkalokayapaharusnyaikam wan laki*)" is containing off record; be vague, the uncle being vague about the object of the FTA, or what the offence is.

Datum 3 : The interaction between a female and female relatives

A : *Uma ai lah bisa stress ulun bediam ditempat kaitu.*
(If I lived in that kind of place, I would be getting stress)

B : *Dasar nyaman disini jua.*
(This is better place to live)

- A : *Tahulah pian ma, menggetar awak ulun bekendaraaan disitu. Rusak banar jalanannya.*
(You know mom, my body were shaking when I rode a motorcycle. I found roads wrecked everywhere)
- B : *Sampai tuntung ikam bekendaraaan leh?*
(Did you ride the motorcycle until you arrived that place?)
- A : *Inggih, kada handak lagi ulun jara dah.*
(Yes, I did. But I won't do it again)

The data above is the conversation between a mother and a daughter, it can be seen the daughter used identity marker *ma* (mom) to address her mother, she also used *inggih* (yes) and honorific *pian* (you) as second person pronoun to show deference. Honorific *pian* (you) is a second person pronoun which considered polite form in *Banjarese*. There are differences between the mother and the daughter in using second pronoun, the mother tends to use *ikam* "you" which considered impolite/neutral. The daughter consistently used polite form when having conversation with her mother. The utterance "tahulah pian ma, menggetar awak ulun bekendaraaan

disitu. Rusak banar jalanannya (you know mom, my body were shaking when I rode a motorcycle. I found roads wrecked everywhere)" is containing positive politeness; intensify interest to H. The speaker may intensify the interest of his own contribution, by making a good story and drawing the hearer as a participant into the conversation with direct question and expression like you know (Brown & Levinson, 2011). In line with Brown and Levinson's statement, the daughter said *tahulah pian ma* (mom you know) to drawing her mom attention.

Datum 4 : The interaction between a female and male relatives

- A : *Uma ai lah, wadai pian nih kadada nang menyamai dasar nyaman.*
(Wow, your cookies is very delicious. I couldn't find the cookies as delicious as yours)
- B : *Iya lo? bahannya nih yang premium barataan pang. Ikam handak kah lagi nih?.*
(I know, right? I used premium ingredients only. Do you want it again?)
- A : *Nukar satu toples ja gen mang*
(I'll buy a jar of cookies)
- B : *Nah, Amang barii ikam dua toples*
(Here, I'll give you two jars)
- A : *Alhamdulillah...*
(Alhamdulillah...)

The conversation above is the interaction between an uncle and his niece. The niece used honorific *pian* (you) which considered as a polite form and the uncle tend to choose second honorific *ikam* (you) which considered as a impolite/neutral form yet he used identity marker *amang* (I/Uncle) as a first person pronoun which considered as polite/neutral form. The utterance "uma ai lah, wadai pian nih kadada nang menyamai

dasar nyaman (wow, your cookies is very delicious. I couldn't find the cookies as delicious as yours) is containing positive politeness; exaggerate.

Datum 5 : The interaction between a male and his spouse

- A : *Ding, kawalah meambilakan wadah-wadah tuh?*
(Dear, can you bring me those food containers?)
- B : *Ini kah kak?*
(This one?)
- A : *Inggih*
(Yes)

The interaction between the husband and his wife contains negative politeness; be conventionally

indirect. The husband used identity marker *ding* (dear) to call his wife and be more direct when asking for help. He also used *inggi* (yes) which considered as polite form. His wife used identity marker *kak* (dear) to mention her husband. Both of them choose identity marker as a politeness marker which create intimacy between them.

Datum 6 : The interaction between a female and her spouse

- A : Kenapa kada wadah Rahmat aja?
(Why don't you go to Rahmat's optic?)
- B : Nyamannya rahmat nih inya minus ja, kalo abah plus minus pang
(Rahmat is very lucky, he got myopia. I got myopia and hypermetropia)
- A : Mending pian wadah martapura ja bah ai
(Maybe, it is better if you go Martapura's optic Dad)
- B : Barangnya sama ja dari Jakarta jua berataan
(They also got all the stuff from Jakarta)

The conversation above is the interaction between a husband and a wife. The wife used indirect language when they speak to her husband. During the conversation, both of them used honorific *pian* (you) as a second person pronoun which considered polite. The wife used hedge "maybe" and tend to choose indirect language when deliver his opinion. It can be concluded that the wife try to show deference to the husband. Compounding hedges and indirect language can increase the politeness expression (Mills, 2004). The wife employs negative politeness; question and hedge, "Mending *pian wadah martapura ja bah ai*" (Maybe, it is better if you go *Martapura's optic Dad*) contains hedge. He offers something which requires his accepting (Brown & Levinson, 2011).

2. The politeness strategies is used by American

Datum 7 : The interaction between a male and male relatives

- A : Let's get the best room. The race is on
- B : But they say the first one come, the first one served, Bro

The speaker use "Bro" as politeness markers, he convey in-group membership which implicitly claim the common ground with hearer that is carried by that definition of the group. The conversation above is considered as positive politeness which 'use in-group markers', (Keeping Up with the Kardashians; Season 8)

Datum 8 : The interaction between a male and female relatives

- A : What's shaking in here?
- B : Oh, kim's giving us some...
- A : Who's pregnant now? You can't be...

The conversation begin when the speaker ask regarding the situation in the room, he wanted to know what has happening. His utterance "what's shaking in here?" is categorized as a positive politeness. He gives his attention and notice the situation between them, (Keeping Up with the Kardashians; season 8).

Datum 9 : The interaction between a female and male relatives

- A : I missed this place and I missed you.
- B : Oh, Khloe. How are you?

The conversation is between two relatives that have just met, it can be seen from the utterance "I missed this place and I missed you." the interaction between them both are very casual and friendly. The woman employs positive politeness; exaggerate. She expressed her longing to her brother in-law and exaggerates the intonation, stress, and other aspects of prosodic.

Datum 10 : Theinteraction between a female and female relatives

- A : Hey, mom. I'm not feeling too great, so I don't think I'm gonna make it today.
- B : Oh, no. I'm so sorry, honey.

Data 28 is the conversation between a woman and her mother, the utterance “hey, mom. I’m not feeling too great, so I don’t think I’m gonna make it today” is considered as negative politeness; apologize. By apologizing for doing an FTA, the speaker can indicate his reluctance to impinge on H’s negative and thereby redress that impingement. She delivers overwhelming reasons that force the speaker for doing FTA, (Keeping Up with the Kardashians; Season 9).

Datum 11 : The interaction between a male and his spouse

- A : This is so beautiful
B : This is we’re in Italy, honey
A : It is like in Italy

The conversation above is the interaction between a husband and wife, when his wife stated “this is we’re in Italy, honey” and the husband answered “it’s like in Italy”. It can be seen the husband tried to avoid disagreement. He use “hedging opinion” and use “it’s like”. The wife using the endearment “honey” as she show her respect and love to her husband which show that woman often use a variety of speaking style. (Keeping up with the Kardashians; Season 5).

Datum 12 : The interaction between a female and her spouse

- A : I’ve put zucchini and some grated carrot.
B : Perhaps, the baby spinach, you’d blanch it or anything?
A : You cook the nutrients out of it. It’s better like that.

The conversation began when the wife entered the kitchen and saw his husband cook. His wife’s utterance “Perhaps, the baby spinach, you’d blanch it or anything?” is considered as negative politeness; be pessimistic. She used pessimistic Hedges ‘perhaps’ in order to redress her husband’s negative face. The interaction between the husband and wife above is containing politeness markers “giving reasons”. The utterance “you cook the nutrients out of it. it’s better like that”, the husband gave a reasons as to why he wants what he wants by including hearer thus in his practical reasoning and assuming reflexivity. In other words, giving reasons is a way implying (Brown & Levinson, 2011), (Mummy Yummy; Season 1)

VI. CONCLUSION

The result reveals that *Banjarese* used positive politeness, negative politeness, and off-record to their relatives. It has been determined that *Banjarese* tend to employ indirect speech form which makes the utterance more polite. Then, *Banjarese* also use honorific to address their interlocutors which determined the social status of the hearer. Based on the data, *Banjarese* male paid more respect to their relatives in using politeness strategy. They tend to choose positive politeness, negative politeness and off record when they interact to their relatives. In addition, *Banjarese* female concentrated on expressing their personal feeling through drawing the hearer to the conversation or making the offers. The last, *Banjarese* female is better than male in giving compliment.

In term of politeness, American people tend to use positive politeness, negative politeness, and bald on record. Different with *Banjarese*, they do not have distinctive politeness such as honorifics to address their interlocutor. American male often use politeness marker such as Bro to address their interlocutor to make the interlocutor feel accepted. American female also use identity marker such as Honey to address their interlocutor. Furthermore, American female tend to exaggerate their utterance which make the interlocutor feel accepted and appreciated.

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